

Study On Cultivation Of Straw Mushroom *Volvariella Volvacea* (Bul. Ex Fr.) Singer On Three Different Substrates

Khin Swe Swe Htun*, Moe Sandar Shein**

Abstract

The effect of different substrates on yield, yield parameters and morphological characters of *Volvariella volvacea* were studied under natural conditions in the months of December 2018 to February 2019. Paddy straw, water-hyacinth and waste paper cardboard were used as a growing medium for cultivation of straw mushroom spawn. Growth and production of fruiting bodies on paper cardboard substrate was higher than the paddy straw and water-hyacinth. The production of fruiting bodies on water-hyacinth substrate was scanty in recent study. The results showed that paper cardboards were good substrate for the mycelial growth and production of fruiting bodies.

Key words : *Volvariella volvacea*, Paddy straw, water-hyacinth, paper cardboard, growing medium

Introduction

Paddy straw mushroom is a popular variety among people because of its distinct flavor, pleasant tastes, higher protein content and shorter cropping duration compared to other cultivated mushrooms. Paddy straw mushroom (*Volvariella volvacea*) is a world famous edible mushroom variety that has high demand due to its deliciousness and nutritive value.

Elaine and Nair, (2009) state that mushroom cultivation activities can play an important role in supporting the local economy by contributing to subsistence food security, nutrition, and medicine; generating additional employment and income through local, regional and national trade. Indirectly, mushroom cultivation also provides opportunities for improving the sustainability of small farming systems through the recycling of organic matter, which can be used as a growing substrate, and then returned to the land as fertilizer. According to Reyes and Abella, (1997) the productivity of mushroom can be increased by selecting locally available suitable substrates. So the cultivation of mushroom using the agro waste is a way of reducing environmental waste materials. Anon, (1983) reported that the yield of straw mushroom depends on the cultivation methods and compost (growing) medium. Straw alone is not sufficient as a composting material as it contains a little quantity nutrients and has a slow rate of decomposition. The objectives of present study are; to study the cultivation of straw mushroom on different nutrient substrate and to evaluate the economic values of straw mushroom.

Materials and Methods

The cultivation of straw mushroom was done under natural conditions during December 2018 to February 2019.

Materials

Volvariella volvacea spawn was selected for study because it is particularly common in Myanmar. It is also mostly preferred by many consumers because its aroma and taste. In the present research, paddy straw, water-hyacinth and paper cardboard were used as a substrate medium and 9 bags of straw mushroom spawn were used. In addition, cow dung and urea were used as nitrogen supplement. Thermometers were used to record and control the bed temperature about between (30-35°C) daily.

* Dr., Lecturer, Department of Botany, Bago University

** Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Botany, Bago University

Methods

Preparation of mushroom bed

Prepare the soil where the beds are to be made by spading an area approximately 2 feet wide, 3 inches deep and 4 feet long for 3 replicates (R1, R2, R3) as shown in Figure (2). Expose this area to the sun for 3-4 days in order to kill any existing bacteria and fungi. Three types of growing media were prepared using paddy straw, water-hyacinth and paper cardboard as seen in Figure (3-5).

Cultivation steps

Treatment 1- Paddy straw compost (T1)

Thirty clean and uncrumpled paddy straw bundles were used for preparation of three layers bed. Soaking dried paddy straw bundled in water for overnight as seen in Figure (6). Then lay down 10 soaked paddy straw bundles side by side as the first layer of the pile. The spawn was placed the straws around the periphery of all the layers of the bed, then sprinkle supplementary food (cow dung) over this area (about 2 viss per layer) and water thoroughly. This completes the first layer of the bed. In this study, a bed composed of three layers is being made. Hence the use of one-third of a bag of spawn per layer. Totally one bag of mushroom spawn were used for each bed. Repeat this procedure to complete subsequent layers, then three buckets of water and one bucket of water mix with straw tonic 0.06 kg supplement were sprinkle thoroughly. The complete bed was then covered with transparent plastic sheet about 1 ft high above the ground level to increase the temperature and to control the humidity. Cover the plastic sheets with dry paddy straw or other leaf twigs. This will prevent direct sunlight from shining on the beds which is likely to kill the spawn (Figure 3,7,8,9).

Treatment 2- Water-hyacinth compost (T2)

Fresh water-hyacinth was chopped manually and the growing media were prepared with water-hyacinth (26 viss) were used (Figure 4). The spawn (1 bag) was sprinkled on the substrates and then covered with cow dung (6 viss). Then 3 buckets of water and one bucket of water mix with straw tonic 0.06 kg supplement were sprinkle thoroughly. After the bed is ready, cover it with transparent plastic sheet as the same method were used.

Treatment 3 - Paper cardboard (T3)

Soak the paper cardboard for 1 hr in water and cut into small pieces. The growing beds were prepared with the cow dung (20 viss) and (2.5 viss) of soaked paper cardboard (Figure 5). The spawn (1 bag) was sprinkled on the substrates and then covered with cow dung (3.5 viss). Then 3 buckets of water and one bucket of water mix with straw tonic 0.06 kg supplement were sprinkle thoroughly. After the bed is ready, cover it with transparent plastic sheet as the same method were used. All of these treatments were made three replicates (R1, R2, R3) for data collection.

Care of mushroom bed

Thermometers were used to collect the day and night temperature in each bed during the growing period. Check the moisture content of the beds on day 5 ((Figure 10).

Harvesting

The straw mushroom is harvested before the volva breaks or just after rupture. (Ahlawat and Tewari, 2007). In the present study mushroom were harvested once two days after 17days they have been sown. Totally, they have been harvested 10 times. Total crop cycle is completed within 4-5 weeks time.

Results

The effect of different substrates on yield, yield parameters and morphological characters of *Volvariella volvacea* was studied under natural conditions in the months of December 2018 and January 2019. The observations were recorded for spawn run, pinhead stage, tiny button stage, button stage, egg stage, elongation stage and mature stage from each treatment (Figure 12-17). The whitish mycelia (pinhead stage) colonized at 8 days in rice straw substrate and 9 days in water-hyacinth and paper cardboard substrate after spawning. The fresh weight of fruiting bodies (button and egg stage) was also recorded and compared the three substrates.

Data Collection and Analysis

The weight of fruiting body, growth production and total cost were recorded. Eight days after planting, whitish mycelia colonized all the substrates. Few days later fruit bodies were observed firstly on the paddy straw, then water-hyacinth compost and 3 days later on the mixture of paper cardboard.

Table 1. Comparison on yields of mushroom on first cultivation bed of three substrates

R1 Treatments	Days										Total viss
	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	33	35	
rice straw substrate (T1)	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.45	0.44	0.27	0.23	0.3	0.25	0.15	2.99
water- hyacinth substrate (T2)	0.09	0.25	0.23	0.11	0.24	0.25	0.18	0.12	0.08	0.07	1.62
paper cardboard substrate (T3)	0.23	0.45	0.52	0.36	0.45	0.7	0.34	0.33	0.16	0.11	3.65

Table 2. Comparison on yields of mushroom on second cultivation bed of three substrates

R2 Treatments	Days										Total viss
	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	33	35	
rice straw substrate (T1)	0.15	0.3	0.28	0.33	0.42	0.28	0.35	0.45	0.15	0.11	2.82
water- hyacinth substrate (T2)	0.11	0.23	0.18	0.31	0.24	0.25	0.18	0.08	0.07	0.06	1.71
paper cardboard substrate (T3)	0.2	0.35	0.25	0.3	0.25	0.23	0.45	0.35	0.6	0.3	3.28

Table 3. Comparison on yields of mushroom on third cultivation bed of three substrates

R3 Treatments	Days										Total viss
	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	33	35	
rice straw substrate (T1)	0.38	0.3	0.22	0.38	0.29	0.37	0.46	0.32	0.16	0.12	3.00
water- hyacinth substrate (T2)	0.16	0.19	0.2	0.11	0.24	0.25	0.28	0.12	0.07	0.05	1.67
paper cardboard substrate (T3)	0.14	0.1	0.23	0.37	0.6	0.23	0.55	0.35	0.45	0.2	3.22

Table 4. Total yields of mushroom in three replicate of each treatment

Treatments	R1 (viss)	R2 (viss)	R3 (viss)	Total yield	Treatment Mean(\bar{X})
Treatment 1	2.99	2.82	3.00	8.81	2.94
Treatment 2	1.62	1.71	1.67	5.00	1.67
Treatment 3	3.65	3.28	3.22	10.15	3.38
Grand Total(G)	8.26	7.81	7.89	23.96	7.99
Grand Mean	2.75	2.60	2.63	7.99	2.66

Table 5. Comparison on cost of different material, income and profit

Treatments	Material cost in kyats	Labor cost in kyats	Total cost in kyats	Income in kyats	Profit in kyats
Treatment 1	9700	2500	12200	35200	23000
Treatment 2	7950	2500	10450	20000	9550
Treatment 3	10700	2500	13200	40600	27400

Fig. 1- Comparison on total cost and income of different treatments

Figure 2. Preparation of mushroom bed

Figure 3. Paddy straw substrate

Figure 4. Water-hyacinth substrate

Figure 5. Paper cardboard substrate

Figure 6. Soaking dried rice straw bundled in water

Figure 7. Placed the spawn around the straws

Figure 8. Roofing frame with bamboo sticks

Figure 9. Cover the plastic sheets with dry rice straw or other leaf twigs

Figure 10. Twisting of rice straw to check the moisture content

Figure 11. Sprinkling with water if necessary

Figure 12. Pinhead stage

Figure 13. Tiny button stage

Figure 14. Button stage

Figure 15. Egg stage

Figure 16. Elongation stage

Figure 17. Mature stage

Discussion and Conclusion

The production of mushrooms is increasing rapidly throughout the world, which is available all round the year and is used in many kinds of dishes. Mushrooms are important sources income for most rural populations in developing countries (Boa, 2006). According to Jiskani, (1999) different agricultural and/or industrial straw wastes can be used for cultivation of mushrooms. The presence of agricultural wastes poses disposal problems as well as causing environmental pollution. The wastes are either burnt or left to rot openly thereby creating a health hazard to human life. The use of these wastes in the cultivation of edible mushrooms will enhance the biological recycling of nutrients (Madan *et al.*, 1987).

In the present study, paddy straw, water-hyacinth and waste paper cardboard were used as a substrate medium for cultivation of straw mushroom spawn. In addition, cow dung and urea were used as nitrogen supplement. The paddy straw was the traditional agro waste substrate for the growth of the straw mushroom. The results showed that the rice straw, water-hyacinth and paper cardboard were naturally supported the mycelial growth and production of fruiting bodies. This result was agreed with Madan *et al.*, (1987) and Jiskani, (1999) for use of low cost waste material and agro wastes substrate in the cultivation of *V. volvacea*.

Mushroom mycelia grow well with the temperature range between 20 and 30°C. Substrate moisture content should be 60-75%. During fruiting, different relative humidity levels, ranging from 80-95%, are needed at the early, mid and later stage. Being aerobic fungi, mushrooms need fresh air during growing and ventilation is more required for reproductive stage (Imtiaj and Rahman. 2008). In the present study, thermometers were used to record and control the bed temperature about between (30-35°C) daily. Check the moisture content of the beds on day 5.

The whitish mycelia (pinhead stage) colonized at 8 days in rice straw substrate and 9 days in water-hyacinth and paper cardboard substrate after spawning (Fig 11). The first cultivation bed of paddy straw (R1) yielded 2.99 viss of fruiting body while the second cultivation bed (R2) yielded 2.82 viss and the third cultivation bed (R3) produced 3.00 viss respectively as shown in Table (1-3). The total yield of mushroom was 8.81 viss and the treatment mean \bar{X} was 2.94 viss were produced in T1 substrate (Table 4).

The first cultivation bed of water-hyacinth (R1) yielded 1.62 viss of fruiting body while the second cultivation bed (R2) yielded 1.71 viss and the third cultivation bed (R3) produced

1.67 viss respectively as shown in Table (1-3). The total yield of mushroom was 5.00 viss and the treatment mean \bar{X} was 1.67 viss were produced in T2 substrate (Table 4).

The first cultivation bed of paper cardboard (R1) yielded 3.65 viss of fruiting body while the second cultivation bed (R2) yielded 3.28 viss and the third cultivation bed (R3) produced 3.22 viss respectively as shown in Table (1-3). The total yield of mushroom was 10.15 viss and the treatment mean \bar{X} was 3.38 viss were produced in T3 substrate. A significantly higher yield (10.15 viss) was observed in paper cardboard substrate while the lowest value (5.00 viss) was observed from water-hyacinth (Table 4). According to this data the growth and production of fruiting bodies on paper cardboard substrate was higher than the paddy straw and water-hyacinth were observed. The production of fruiting bodies on water-hyacinth substrate was scanty. This may be the new seedling of water-hyacinth grown on the old water-hyacinth.

The total cost of paper cardboard treatment was the highest value (13200 kyats) than the total cost of paddy straw treatment (12200 kyats) and water-hyacinth treatment (10450 kyats) as seen in Table 5 and Figure 1. In the local market, the prize value of mushroom was about 3500-4000 kyats in viss. The profit of paper cardboard treatment (27400 kyats) was higher than the profit of the other two treatments, paddy straw (23000 kyats) and water-hyacinth (9550 kyats). Among them, the profit of water-hyacinth was low. Therefore, it assumed that the paper cardboard treatment of mushroom had the higher profit compared to the water-hyacinth and rice straw treatments. The results show that the yields of mushroom were influenced by different substrates.

In this study, the cultivation is dependent on waste materials and the agricultural raw material that are cheaply available. It involves less investment but the grower can get more return. The results of the study have indicated that the mushroom (*V. volvacea*) production is economically feasible as it can give maximum net return by reducing their cost of production. This paper summarizes a wide range of information on the production of paddy straw mushroom and its social and economic importance for the region.

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